

Stability Constants of Orthocarboxyphenyl di(*p*-tolyl) arsine Complexes

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Manuscript received 30 August 1974; accepted 2 May 1975

The proton-ligand stability constant of orthocarboxyphenyl di(*p*-tolyl) arsine and the stepwise stability constants of its complexes with Ni(II), Cu(II), Hg(II), UO₂(II), La(III) and Ce(III) have been determined in ethanol-water (70 : 30, v/v) system by potentiometric method at 30° and 40° at $\mu = 0.1 M$. The values of $\log K_{1H}$ are 6.38 at 30° and 6.26 at 40°. The order of stability constants for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes has been found to be Hg(II) > UO₂(II) > Cu(II) > Ni(II) whereas La(III) > Ce(III) is the order for 1 : 1 complexes.

THE study of metal complexes of ligands containing arsenic is of immense importance as the organoarsenic compounds are the important fungicides which are extensively employed to protect the crops from the pathological diseases.

From the chemistry point of view the arsenic containing compounds have a capability to form π back bonding with metal ions having filled non-bonding *d* orbitals. The transition metal ions are of interest as they have a capacity for supplying π bonding electrons. So, it was considered desirable to study the stabilities of their complexes with orthocarboxyphenyl di(*p*-tolyl) arsine. The present investigation describes the determination of the proton-ligand stability constant and the stepwise metal ligand stability constants using Bjerrum-Calvin^{1,2}, *pH* titration technique as was modified by Irving and Rossotti³.

Materials and Methods

Methods :

Orthocarboxyphenyl di(*p*-tolyl) arsine was prepared by the method already known and its solution (0.05 *M*) was prepared in absolute ethanol^{4,5}.

All other chemicals used were of BDH Analar grade. Aqueous solutions of nickel(II), nitrate, copper(II) nitrate, mercury(II) chloride, uranyl(II) nitrate, lanthanum(III) nitrate and cerium(III) nitrate were prepared and standardized. The strength of each solution was adjusted to 0.01 *M* by dilution. A 1.0 *M* solution of KNO₃ was prepared by direct weighing and employed to maintain the ionic strength $\mu = 0.1 M$. A solution of KOH was prepared in 70% ethanol-water system and standardized against a standard oxalic acid solution. The

solution of nitric acid was standardized against standard alkali. Double distilled water, free from carbon dioxide was used for preparing all the solutions.

Buffer tablets (BDH) were used to prepare solutions of *pH* 4.0, 7.0 and 9.0.

Apparatus :

A systronic *pH* meter was used with a glass and calomel electrodes assembly. The solutions were maintained at $30.0^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $40.0^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ by using a thermostatic electric water bath.

Procedure :

The *pH* meter was set and checked with buffer solutions of *pH* 4.0, 7.0 and 9.0 prepared from standard buffer tablets.

The ratio of metal ion to ligand was kept 1 : 5 in order to fulfil the maximum coordination number of metal ion. The following mixtures were prepared.

- A 2.0 ml of 0.01 *M* HNO₃
- B 2.0 ml of 0.01 *M* HNO₃ + 2.0 ml of 0.05 *M* CPDTA
- C 0.1 ml of 0.1 *M* HNO₃ + 2.0 ml of 0.05 *M* CPDTA + 2.0 ml of 0.01 *M* metal salt.

The ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 *M* by adding KNO₃ solution and the onset of hydrolysis was checked by the addition of nitric acid. The initial total volume in each case was 40 ml (70% ethanol water system). The *pH* of the solution was plotted versus the volume of the alkali. The shapes of the titration curves were as usual.

Orthocarboxyphenyl di(*p*-tolyl) arsine (CPDTA) behaves as an acid due to the presence of the

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carboxylic acid group. The ligand gets dissociated according to the following process :

The anion formed contains carboxylic acid and an arsine group. Therefore, it behaves as a bidentate chelating agent in solution.

Proton Ligand Stability Constant :

The average number of protons (\bar{n}_A) associated with ligand is defined as :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{n}_A &= \frac{\text{total concentration of protons bound to ligand}}{\text{total concentration of ligand not bound to metal}} \\
 &= \frac{C_{LH} + 2C_{LH_2} + 3C_{LH_3} + \dots + jC_{LH_j}}{C_L + C_{LH} + C_{LH_2} + C_{LH_3} + \dots + C_{LH_j}} \quad \dots (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

in terms of formation constants the equation (1) can be represented as below :

$$\bar{n}_A = \frac{K_1^H C_H + 2K_1^H K_2^H C_H^2 + \dots + jK_1^H \dots K_j^H C_H^j}{1 + K_1^H C_H + K_1^H K_2^H C_H^2 + \dots + K_j^H C_H^j} \quad \dots (2)$$

where j is the maximum number of associated protons.

To calculate the formation constant, the values of \bar{n}_A at different pH were calculated using the acid and ligand titration curves by using Irving and Rossotti³ equation :

$$\bar{n}_A = Y T_{C_{LO}} \frac{(V'' - V')(N^\circ + E^\circ)}{(V^\circ + V') T_{C_{LO}}} \quad \dots (3)$$

where V' and V'' are the volumes of alkali added in acid and ligand titration to reach the same pH value; V° , E° , N° , $T_{C_{LO}}$ are the total initial volume of the titrating mixture, total concentration of acid, total concentration of alkali and the total concentration of the ligand respectively and y is the number of dissociable protons.

The formation curves at 30° and 40° were obtained by plotting \bar{n}_A values against pH . The formation curve is shown in Fig. 1.

Metal Ligand Stability Constants :

For a stepwise complex formation system the formation constants are given by :

$$K_n = \frac{C_{ML_n}}{C_{ML_{n-1}} C_L} \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots N)$$

where K_n is the n th metal ligand stability constant. The stability constants were obtained from the formation curves drawn between \bar{n} and pL where \bar{n} is

Fig. 1. Formation Curves of Proton Ligand Complex for Orthocarboxyphenyl di(para-tolyl) arsine.

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 30.0^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ & \text{O—O} \\
 40.0^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ & \Delta-\Delta
 \end{array}$$

the average number of ligands attached per metal ion and pL is $-\log C_L$. The values of \bar{n} and pL were calculated from the following equations :

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(v''' - v'')(N^\circ + E^\circ)}{(V^\circ + v') \bar{n}_A T_{CM_0}}$$

$$pL = \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n=j} \beta_n^H \left(\frac{1}{\text{antilog } B} \right)^n}{T_{C_{L_0}} - \bar{n} T_{CM_0}} \cdot \frac{V^\circ + v''}{V^\circ - v''} \right]$$

where T_{CM_0} is total metal ion concentration present in solution. β_n^H is the over all proton-ligand stability constant and other terms have their usual meaning.

Results and Discussion

Proton-Ligand System :

Orthocarboxyphenyl di(*p*-tolyl) arsine is insoluble in water but less soluble in ethanol. Due to this reason, 70% ethanol water system was used as a medium. Orthocarboxyphenyl di(*p*-tolyl) arsine contains only one dissociable hydrogen atom. It has been found experimentally that the formation curve (Fig. 1) for the proton-ligand system extends between $\bar{n}_A = 0$ and $\bar{n}_A = 1.0$, showing the one step dissociation of the carboxylic group. The values of $\log K_1^H$ has been determined at two temperatures by using the relationship

$$\log K_1^H = pH + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A}$$

The average values of $\log K_1^H$ are 6.38 and 6.26 (Table 1) at 30° and 40° respectively. These values are in agreement with those obtained by

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ORTHOCARBOXYPHENYL DI(*p*-TOLYL) ARSINE COMPLEX AT IONIC STRENGTH $\mu = 0.1M$

Temperature °C	log K_n	H ⁺	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Hg(II)	UO ₂ (II)	La(III)	Ce(III)
30	log K_1	6.38	2.86	3.76	5.30	4.58*	3.23	3.15**
	log K_2	—	2.60	2.97	3.50	3.62*	2.84	—
	log β_2	—	5.46	6.73	8.80	8.20	6.07	—
40	log K_1	6.26	2.76	3.75	5.16	4.67*	3.23	3.24**
	log K_2	—	2.54	2.93	3.16	3.59*	2.78	—
	log β_2	—	5.30	6.68	8.32	8.26	6.01	—

* Correction term method.

** Linear plot method.

interpolation to half \bar{n} method. The value of log K_1^H decreases with the rise of temperature and hence the acid strength of orthocarboxyphenyl di(*p*-tolyl) arsine increases.

Metal Ligand System

The value of \bar{n} in the case of metal-ligand complexes reaches a value greater than one and less than two except in the case of cerium(III) where it is always less than one (Figs. 2, 3). This indicates the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes of the metal ions Ni(II), Cu(II), Hg(II), UO₂(II) and La(III) with the ligand but 1 : 1 complex in the case of Cerium(III).

The metal ligand stability constants are reported in Table 1. The values have been obtained by correction terms method⁶ in the case UO₂(II) complexes and linear plot method⁷ in the case of Ce(III) complex. However, in the case of Ni(II), Cu(II), Hg(II) and La(III), where these methods were not applicable, the values of log K_1 , log K_2 and log β_2 were calculated by the Bjerrum's half \bar{n} method from the formation curves.

The formation of these complexes occurs in the pH range 3.0 to 7.0 which shows that these are formed in the acid region.

The observed order of stabilities for the divalent metal ions is Hg(II) > UO₂(II) > Cu(II) > Ni(II) and for the trivalent metal ions is La(III) > Ce(III). For the bivalent ions it is according to Irving-Williams order of stabilities⁸. It can be explained on the basis of ratio of effective nuclear charge to the ionic radii. The order of stabilities of bivalent metal ions can also be explained by examining the ionization potentials of these metal ions which are in the same order.

Orthocarboxyphenyl di(*p*-tolyl) arsine ion is a chelating ion containing one arsine group as donor. The arsenic atom contains unfilled *d* orbitals which can form π back bond with the filled *d* orbitals of the metal ion. When one ligand attacks the metal ion, there is donation of electrons from the ligand towards the metal ion at the first stage. This is expected to reduce the positive charge on the metal ions resulting in the decrease of the electron accepting

Fig. 2 Formation curves of orthocarboxyphenyl di(para-tolyl) arsine complexes at 40°C,

Legend

Ni²⁺ O—O
La³⁺ Δ—Δ
Ce³⁺ □—□

Cu²⁺ X—X
UO₂²⁺ ●—●
Hg²⁺ ▲—▲

Fig. 3. Formation curves of orthocarboxyphenyl di(para-tolyl)arsine complexes at 25°C.

Legend

Ni²⁺ ○—○
La³⁺ △—△
Ce³⁺ □—□

Cu²⁺ X—X
UO₂²⁺ ●—●
Hg²⁺ ▲—▲

capacity of the metal ion. Therefore the addition of the second ligand will not be so easier and the value of $\log K_2$ is expected to be much lower than $\log K_1$. But it is not in accordance with the experimental results.

The reason for this deviation is the formation of $d_\pi-d_\pi$ back bonding resulting from the donation of non-bonding d electrons of the metal ion to the vacant d orbitals of the donor atoms. The excessive transfer of charge from the ligand to the metal atom is relieved due to this π back bonding. This causes an increase in the tendency of the metal atom to accept electrons from the second ligand and the higher value of $\log K_2$ is observed. The difference between the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ is not large in the cases of Ni(II) and Cu(II) where the formation of π back bond is easier. From a perusal of the data (Table 1), it is evident that the stabilities are not affected by the change in temperature.

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